

E-RIHS IP

European Research Infrastructure for Heritage Science IMPLEMENTATION Phase

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D4.4 E-RIHS Enlargement Strategy

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ABSTRACT

The document outlines the E-RIHS Enlargement Strategy, submitted as deliverable D4.4 within the E-RIHS IP project, developed as part of Task 4.2 E-RIHS enlargement strategy” in collaboration with Task 2.2. Supporting the establishment of E-RIHS National Nodes”, Task 6.3 “Strengthening E-RIHS cooperation on the EU scene and beyond” and Enlargement Board established in the framework of the project.

The core content reflects the outcomes of fruitful discussions with the Enlargement Board members on different forms of participation and collaboration with E-RIHS ERIC, which included Member States and Associated Countries, Third Countries, as well as individual organisations. The needs of countries or organisations for E-RIHS ERIC assistance in their process to establish the collaboration with E-RIHS ERIC, either as full Members, Observers or participation of individual organisations set the ground of the Enlargement Strategy. It comprises description of different roles within the E-RIHS ERIC, such as the role of the Enlargement Board, Director General, Central Hub, Committee of National Nodes and Heritage Science Academy. Tailored communication and dissemination activities will further enlarge the chances of E-RIHS ERIC for the efficient global growth.

The document guides E-RIHS on its way of becoming a global research infrastructure.

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ABBREVIATIONS

Abbreviations	Expansion
ANTECIPA	Associação Nacional de Pesquisa em Tecnologia e Ciência do Patrimônio /National Association for Research in Technology and Heritage Science
ARCHLAB	Archives and collections laboratory
CHARISMA	Cultural heritage Advanced Research Infrastructures: Synergy for a Multidisciplinary Approach to Conservation/Restoration
CNN	Committee of National Nodes
DG	Director General
DIGILAB	Digital Laboratory
EASSH	European Alliance for Social Sciences and Humanities
EB	Enlargement Board
ERA	European Research Area
ERIC	European Research Infrastructure Consortium
E-RIHS	European Research Infrastructure for Heritage Science
ESFRI	European Strategy Forum on Research Infrastructures
EU	European Union
EU-Artech	Access, research and technology for the conservation of the European cultural heritage
FIXLAB	Large scale facilities and advanced laboratories
G-RI	Global Research Infrastructure
GSO	Group of Senior Officials
HS	Heritage Science
iCNN	Interim Committee of National Nodes of E-RIHS
iGA	Interim General Assembly of E-RIHS
IPERION CH	Integrating Platforms for the European Research Infrastructure ON Cultural Heritage
IPERION HS	Integrating Platforms for the European Research Infrastructure ON Heritage Science
Labs-TECH	Laboratories on Science and Technology for the Conservation of European Cultural Heritage
MOLAB	Mobile Laboratory
RESINFRA LAC	Partnership Research Infrastructures project Latin America and Caribbean
TNA	Trans National Access

1. INTRODUCTION

E-RIHS outstanding network of international cooperation raised the interest of the G7 Group of Senior Officials (GSO) on Global Research Infrastructures in 2014 and in 2015 the E-RIHS community submitted the intention letter to become a Global Research Infrastructure (G-RI). This reflects the openness of E-RIHS to the adhesion or association with EU and non-EU countries and organisations, towards the long-term objective of operating at the global level.

The international collaboration of E-RIHS is of extreme importance on the way to its enlargement and it was thoroughly described in the Cooperation Strategy as a part of the deliverable D6.4 Report on Cooperation Activities. It comprises collaborations with research policy initiatives, other research infrastructures, open cloud ecosystem and other digital initiatives, other EU and non-EU associations (e.g., EASSH), intergovernmental organisations and international collaboration with Third Countries.[1]

Building the E-RIHS community and collaborations within Member States and Associated Countries were already set in the past EU-funded research infrastructure projects, starting in 1999 with Labs-TECH project and followed by EU-Artech, CHARISMA, IPERION CH and IPERION HS. The outstanding collaborations were set in the frame of successful joint research activities, transnational access, training provision and very well-designed communication and dissemination activities. Many of those countries are among the founding Members of the E-RIHS ERIC, with their representatives in the current governing bodies of E-RIHS, *interim* General Assembly (iGA) and *interim* Committee of National Nodes (iCNN).

E-RIHS vision to become a G-RI was already reflected in previous collaboration activities of E-RIHS community within different projects, such as IPERION HS in which four E-RIHS hubs in Brazil, Mexico, and the USA were full partners. Furthermore, E-RIHS developed a three-year pilot action on the exchange of open data in heritage science with Latin America and Caribbean countries that was delivered through the RESINFRA LAC project.

The intention of E-RIHS of becoming a G-RI was already mentioned in the E-RIHS PP Business Plan v.1.01, prepared within the E-RIHS Preparatory Phase project (2017–2020). [2] As stated in the document, E-RIHS ERIC will secure the defragmentation of ERA that will affirm European leadership in heritage science at the global level and empower Europe to build the global research area of heritage science. The most direct impact of E-RIHS ERIC will be the generation and sharing of new knowledge to understand and preserve heritage. The sharing through DIGILAB and access through the E-RIHS Platforms (ARCLAB, MOLAB and FIXLAB) will be open to researchers everywhere leading to the establishment of global relationships. [2]

The Enlargement Strategy of E-RIHS ERIC considers concrete actions to be taken in relation to EU Member States and Associated Countries, as well as Third Countries and individual institutions.

2. ENGAGING WITH E-RIHS ERIC

2.1 Establishment of the Enlargement Board and its role

The Enlargement Board (EB) was established within the E-RIHS IP project in order to bring together the scientists from countries, both within and outside the European Union, that are identified as targets for the E-RIHS Enlargement Strategy. These target countries include those that are either

not yet engaged in E-RIHS or are collaborating with E-RIHS as they explore their interest and potential pathways to formally join the forthcoming ERIC. Currently, the members of the EB are scientists from Norway, Denmark, Germany, Czech Republic, Brazil, US, Egypt and Abu Dhabi Emirate. During the E-RIHS IP project, 3 EB meetings took place as part of Task 4.2 Enlargement Strategy and in collaboration with Task 2.2 Supporting the Establishment of E-RIHS National Nodes.

The EB will continue its function beyond the duration of E-RIHS IP project as an *ad hoc* committee, subject to the approval of the General Assembly of the future ERIC.

The EB *ad hoc* committee operates in close cooperation with the Committee of National Nodes (CNN), guided by the Director General's role in overseeing legal representation and international relations. Supported by the Central Hub and the HS Academy programs, the EB focuses on cultivating intensive contacts in target countries through dedicated events and other initiatives.

The members of the CNN may be invited to EB meetings in order to share their best practices and to plan further collaborations. It is important to note that in E-RIHS IP, the EB was actively led by the iCNN Chair, as the E-RIHS National Coordinators gathered within the CNN play a crucial role in promoting international scientific collaboration and partnerships.

The EB focuses on:

- Discussion and exchange of best practices on the establishment and functioning of a National Node;
- Designing cooperation activities, e.g., access provision, training, projects applications, joint research activities, etc.;
- Discussion on common strategies, e.g., standards, scientific, ethics, etc.;
- Designing common communication and dissemination activities;
- Discussion on measures and actions related to global challenges.

2.2 The role of the Director General

The Director General (DG) acts as legal authority representing E-RIHS ERIC in negotiations with scientists or decision-makers coming from countries that are not yet E-RIHS ERIC Members or Observers. In collaboration with the interested scientific community, the DG directly engages with relevant Embassies, governmental officials and funding agencies to enable decision-makers to better understand the benefits of joining E-RIHS ERIC. Furthermore, in collaboration with CNN, the DG: (i) negotiates customized strategies for each target country, addressing specific national priorities, research strengths, and potential contributions to the ERIC; (ii) establishes Memoranda of Understanding and, upon the approval of GA, Partnership Agreements with individual institutions to secure mutually beneficial terms; and (iii) facilitates research projects or initiatives to promote collaborations with potential new Members or Observers, institutions, associations, networks and stakeholders. The DG is also responsible for issuing endorsement letters to support interested scientific community with their applications for funds related to the establishment of E-RIHS National Node or to stimulate decisions favouring the country's accession to E-RIHS ERIC as Members or Observers. The DG also ensures the smooth legal, administrative and operational integration of new Members or Observers. To enhance global visibility, the DG promotes E-RIHS ERIC's international profile and builds diplomatic relationships by participating in global forums, conferences and tailored partnership meetings organised with local partners of countries interested in exploring their participation in E-RIHS. Assisted by the Central Hub staff, the DG monitors the Enlargement Strategy's progress, provides regular updates on its advancement to GA and other relevant governing bodies, including CNN and Scientific and Ethics Advisory Board, proposes and

implements necessary adjustments to maintain the E-RIHS ERIC's relevance in the European and global research landscapes.

2.3 The role of the Central Hub

The Central Hub assists the functioning of the EB, organisation of EB meetings, Enlargement Workshops, and tailored partnership meetings intended to initiate collaborations with E-RIHS ERIC. Additionally, the Central Hub tracks key performance indicator to monitor the implementation of the E-RIHS ERIC Enlargement Strategy that is further described in the dedicated Chapter 7 on Monitoring.

2.4 The role of the Committee of National Nodes

As the scientific body, the Committee of National Nodes (CNN) plays a pivotal role in expanding the scientific reach of E-RIHS by ensuring that the scientific strategies and priorities of new Members, Observers or individual organisations cooperating with E-RIHS are harmonized with those of existing members, thereby creating mutual added-value.

Within the process of the E-RIHS ERIC enlargement, the CNN collaborates with the DG in carrying out the related tasks, which fall under his/her responsibility (see § 2.2 The role of Director General), and plays a role in facilitating an easier transition of an EU Member State or Associated Country to become a Member or Observer, or collaborations with Third Countries.

As distributed infrastructure, each E-RIHS National Node adopts the organisational structure that best fits its national context, while ensuring efficient participation and contribution to the ERIC. In the framework of the enlargement strategy, a twinning approach, where well-established Nodes share their best practices and organisational structures with under preparation National Nodes, is beneficial. This approach provides new Nodes with the opportunity to learn from the experience of well-established National Nodes with similar characteristics, while adapting those practices most suitable to their national context. Such an approach also facilitates the adoption and implementation of the ERIC's operational policies by new Nodes.

Through this process, CNN members can help develop an E-RIHS-aligned community nationally. This includes providing advice to national heritage science communities in the development of Memoranda of Understanding or Consortium Agreements critical for the operation of Nodes on national levels, helping with the alignment with ESFRI principles, organising events in collaboration with such communities, etc. The process of development of a national community that can efficiently engage decision- and policy-makers at national levels is a long one, especially in countries where such communities are still disperse.

As part of the process, CNN members are invited to give their input at the EB meetings, Enlargement Workshops and tailored partnership meetings organised with local partners. Bilateral meetings can also be organised.

2.5 The role of the HS Academy

HS Academy, through its diverse programme, aims at delivering worldclass training to scientists and practitioners in the sector, resulting in an outstanding impact on the promotion, exchange and transfer of best practices in heritage science internationally. Through its training activities, the HS Academy promotes inclusion and international collaboration, as well as promotes E-RIHS best practices and access. As many HS Academy activities take place online or in hybrid format, global participation is straightforward, as well as desired.

In-person training programmes are organised in the form of workshops, doctoral schools and other types of hands-on training, normally in E-RIHS ERIC member countries. For the purpose of engagement of communities in target countries, selected in-person training activities can be organised in such countries as well. These can comprise different aspects of the HS domain, such as hands-on instrumental research, data interpretation, preventive conservation, site management etc. and can focus on training of users, providers or research infrastructure managers.

E-RIHS further promotes exchange of best talent by offering E-RIHS ERIC access to early career researchers in the domain of heritage science, thereby providing hands-on learning opportunities and experience. By becoming part of the E-RIHS ERIC user group, such early career researchers remain associated with E-RIHS and become its ambassadors in their respective countries.

E-RIHS takes part in the development and delivery of training initiatives through EU and international mobility programmes such as ERASMUS, thereby promoting its values and engaging learners well outside the E-RIHS member countries.

Intergovernmental organisations can play an important role in the training provision at the global level as reflected in one of the points of the cooperation agreement signed between ICCROM and E-RIHS in October 2018, which will be further explored as part of ICCROM's contribution as a Permanent Observer in E-RIHS ERIC.

3. TAILORED COMMUNICATION AND DISSEMINATION ACTIVITIES FOR ENLARGEMENT

E-RIHS developed a sound Communication and Dissemination Strategy [3] with a focus on several objectives, such as support internal communications to strengthen the commitment to the research infrastructure, create a collaborative environment at a global level for the protection of heritage, strengthen the E-RIHS presence in the RI environment and the E-RIHS cohesion in the heritage science community, increase the visibility of E-RIHS by communicating scientific results, enhance the impact of E-RIHS outcomes by disseminating and translating them into actionable insights for stakeholders, including practitioners and policy-makers, engage the target audience and the public, involve users and new communities, etc.

Related to the E-RIHS ambition of its enlargement and becoming a global research infrastructure a special focus is placed on the organisation of Enlargement Workshops and tailored partnership meetings with local partners of countries interested in exploring their participation in or collaboration with E-RIHS.

3.1 Enlargement Workshops

The E-RIHS ERIC Enlargement Strategy includes the organisation, on the yearly basis, of at least one dedicated Enlargement Workshop.

The purpose of the E-RIHS Enlargement Workshop is to stimulate the interest of scientists and decision-makers to join the E-RIHS ERIC network and discuss the possibilities for further collaboration. For EU Member States and Associated Countries, this serves as one of the first steps towards the full Membership or Observer status.

As part of E-RIHS IP project, a successful Enlargement Workshop was organised. The online format, composed of the three parts—Opening Session, Bilateral Sessions and Closing Session—proved to be

highly effective. These sessions were spread out over several days, allowing ample time for reflection and preparation between each part. At the Opening Session, the E-RIHS's vision, mission, access projects, development of access provision and training provision were presented. The following Bilateral Sessions were organised together with interested scientists and/or decision-makers in order to plan further collaboration activities. At the Closing Session, the summary of the outcomes of Bilateral Sessions was presented. The format was successful because it allowed the Opening Session to address cross-cutting topics of interest to the diverse scientific communities invited to participate, the Bilateral Sessions to tackle specific issues, and the Closing Session to report on matters of interest to the various communities. The description and outcomes of the first Enlargement Workshop, organised within E-RIHS IP project by Task 2.2 Supporting the Establishment of E-RIHS National Nodes and Task 4.2 Enlargement Strategy are gathered in Annex 1.

The Enlargement Workshop format, tested as part of E-RIHS IP project, is being transferred as a best practice within E-RIHS ERIC, with adaptations to be made each time to suit the target countries, individual organisations, and their specific needs.

3.2 Tailored partnership meetings

The E-RIHS Enlargement Strategy includes tailored partnership meetings organised in collaboration with local partners interested in exploring collaboration and participation in E-RIHS. These meetings aim at raising awareness of E-RIHS activities and participation opportunities, targeting both scientists and decision-makers. The content is customised to the needs of local partners and covers a range of topics, from the functioning and policies of E-RIHS to specific scientific issues and advancements. These meetings may take the form of sessions, workshops or webinars, involving representatives from National Nodes, to promote the latest scientific advancements in heritage science and showcase results of selected access projects. The exchange in the latest scientific advancements during these meetings serves as a basis to identify common interests and facilitate further planning of different collaboration activities (e.g., common projects applications, training, staff exchange, etc.).

4. STRATEGY RELATED TO MEMBER STATES AND ASSOCIATED COUNTRIES

The international collaboration activities of E-RIHS have so far resulted in excellent contacts in many countries; however, these are not evenly distributed across Europe or globally. In terms of the preparedness of E-RIHS ERIC to enter negotiations with new potential member countries, E-RIHS will work with the EU Member States and Associated Countries, as well as with Third Countries according to the following priorities in terms of interest:

- (1) Countries, which have collaborated in E-RIHS preparatory projects and in the iGA, but are not ready to sign the ERIC. These countries are most embedded in the ESFRI culture and will require least effort to engage.
- (2) EU Member States, Associated Countries, and Third Countries where there is an existing relationship or a legal platform and where starting the process of negotiation might be doable, but will take more time. Working with Third Countries might require a specific approach both legally and organisationally, therefore, it is described in a separate Chapter.

- (3) Working with other countries, where we need mechanisms yet to be developed on a case-by-case basis, and where E-RIHS ERIC might be in the position to start negotiating only in a year's time or later.

Based on their experience the CNN members can have a crucial tutoring role and help the interested scientific communities with advice on how to build the National Node, how to approach the policy decision makers, how to attract funding, etc. in order to reach the final goal of joining E-RIHS ERIC (see § 2.3 The role of Committee of National Nodes). Further supported by the DG and Central Hub, EB activities and Enlargement Workshops, the communities will be efficiently guided to prepare the documentation and approach their relevant Ministries.

The Observer status can be the first step before becoming a full Member of the E-RIHS ERIC. A special attention is put to defining access provision with the country interested in joining the E-RIHS ERIC as a full Member. This demands involvement of CNN and comprises also negotiations related to the selection of access services in order to achieve complementarity with the existing E-RIHS ERIC Catalogue of Services. Moreover, based on the negotiated services, the in-kind contribution of the country has to be defined and included in the Service Level Agreement, while the annual membership fee contribution is calculated by the Central Hub according to the algorithm outlined in Annex II Financial of the E-RIHS ERIC Statutes.

5. STRATEGY RELATED TO THIRD COUNTRIES

Considering the ambition of E-RIHS to establish a global research infrastructure, it is quite important for the Third Countries to be engaged in the E-RIHS ERIC activities. For non-EU countries empowered to sign the participation to E-RIHS ERIC, accepting all the implications contained in such a legal form, a solution could be the standard partnership, to be achieved via negotiation with the proper governmental bodies, as either Members or Observers [2].

The European Research Infrastructure Consortium (ERIC) is a unique legal entity under EU law, adopted in 2009 to facilitate the establishment and operation of European Research Infrastructures. Although the ERIC allows participation by non-EU countries (in addition to EU Associated Countries and intergovernmental organisations), only a limited number of non-EU countries have joined an ERIC as full members to date. From a legal perspective, the main reasons could be summarised as follows:

- Reluctance to accept the jurisdiction of the European Court over litigation among the members of the ERIC or between the members of the ERIC and the ERIC as well as over any other litigation to which the European Union is a party (as required by Art. 15 of the ERIC Regulation).
- The requirement that Member States or Associated Countries must jointly hold the majority of the voting rights in the assembly of members (Art. 9(3) of the ERIC Regulation).
- Concern (whether justified or not) that a decision taken by the assembly of members would cause a non-EU member to breach their national laws.
- Inability to take part in the EU legislative process as non-EU countries are not represented in the Council, the European Parliament or indeed any of the committees.
- Other practical legal issues may stand in the way, due to the fact that the ERIC Regulation remains silent on issues such as work permit for international staff employed or seconded by a non-EU member to the ERIC; import and export of equipment from outside the EU, etc. [4]

For countries not in the position of directly participating in the ERIC, which in the end could represent the majority of countries for a (potential) global RI, an initial solution could be that of bilateral agreements (partnership agreements). These agreements are to be negotiated case by case, based on the country's expectations, the needs from the E-RIHS ERIC, as well as their contributions to the E-RIHS ERIC.

As the result of activities of the Enlargement Strategy, the Director General, assisted by Central Hub and in collaboration with CNN, guides the negotiations with institutions from Third Countries to prepare their offer to the E-RIHS ERIC as part of the partnership agreement, including mutual commitments for the collaboration.

5.1 Formalising collaboration

As an initial step towards the formal collaboration, a Memorandum of Understanding (MoU) is signed between E-RIHS ERIC and the interested institution from a Third Country. This will further facilitate negotiations on expectations, needs and offerings of the institution coming from a Third Country and can result in a more legally binding Partnership Agreement. The template of MoU is presented in Annex 2. E-RIHS ERIC can sign MoU and Partnership Agreement with an individual institution from a Third Country, or with the institution representing the National Node or the network of institutions from the Country.

During the E-RIHS IP project, the most advanced negotiations and the MoU currently in preparation are with the Brazilian Infrastructure ANTECIPA and with the Egyptian network of HS institutions represented by the Ain Shams University, Cairo. The draft of their expectations and needs, as well as their offer to the E-RIHS ERIC are presented in Annex 3.

6. COLLABORATION OPPORTUNITIES WITH INDIVIDUAL ORGANISATIONS

For individual organisations, whether they are institutions in countries that are not yet Members or Observers of E-RIHS ERIC, or associations, international organisations or intergovernmental organisations that are either unable to become ERIC member, or whose collaboration with ERIC does not require mutual commitments in that regard, there are several opportunities for collaboration across various areas such as scientific strategy, access services, training, outreach, management, policy, technology transfer and data management.

Each collaboration between E-RIHS ERIC and interested organisation(s) will be the result of negotiations case by case and formalised as part of specific research projects or through dedicated tailored agreements. Where possible and appropriate, every effort has to be made to ensure that bilateral tailored agreements transition into full participation in the ERIC, in accordance with the modalities outlined in the Statutes.

Below is a non-exhaustive list of examples of how these collaborations can be implemented within the different areas in which E-RIHS operates.

Collaboration opportunities in scientific strategy:

- Specific joint actions for creating new research prospects, including the identification of research priorities.
- Exchanges of experience and expertise;

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- Consortia creation for transnational calls to secure funding support for targeted projects.

Collaboration opportunities in access services:

- Provision of access services, subject to certain conditions;
- Access to facilities;
- Contributing to shaping user strategies to better align access policy with user needs.

Collaboration opportunities in training:

- Developing of training modules;
- Participation and promotion in seminars, lectures, workshops;
- Staff and students exchanges.

Collaboration opportunities in outreach:

- Conception and/or promotion of dissemination activities to increase awareness of citizens, stakeholders, policy makers;
- Reaching new communities.

Collaboration opportunities in the management of processes:

- Supporting and sharing best practices for risk management, quality system, etc.

Collaboration opportunities in policy and standards:

- Bringing expertise;
- Working on policy alignment or common practices, etc.

Collaboration opportunities in technology transfer:

- Developing innovation promotion activities;
- Participating in the marketing strategy, etc.

Collaboration opportunities in data management:

- Supporting the sharing, use and sustainability of digital resources (e.g., data, tools, etc.);
- Developing protocols, workflows, etc.

7. MONITORING

The Central Hub of E-RIHS ERIC has the task of gathering the Enlargement Strategy (ES) Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) on the yearly basis. On the basis of these KPIs, the Director General provides regular updates on the Enlargement strategy advancement to GA and other relevant governing bodies, including CNN and Scientific and Ethics Advisory Board. The subsequent analysis of the results serves as the basis for preparing the activity plan for the following year.

7.1 Key performance indicators for the E-RIHS Enlargement Strategy

The E-RIHS ERIC Enlargement Strategy (ES) envisages the following key performance indicators for tracking its progress:

Enlargement Board (EB) members KPI_{ESEB}:

KPI_{ESEB}1: Number of EB members

KPI_{ESEB}2: Number of EB meetings

Endorsement letters (EL) KPI_{ESEL}:

KPI_{ESEL}1: Number of endorsement letters issued by the Director General

Bilateral Meetings (BM) KPI_{ESBM}:

KPI_{ESBM}1: Number of bilateral meetings with new potential Members, Observers or individual organisation interested in collaborating with E-RIHS ERIC

KPI_{ESBM}2: Number of meetings between CNN and EB

Training (T) KPI_{EST}:

KPI_{EST}1: Number of on-line webinars organised with new potential Members, Observers or individual organisation interested in collaborating with E-RIHS ERIC

KPI_{EST}2: Number of delivered hands on trainings organised with new potential Members, Observers or individual organisation interested in collaborating with E-RIHS ERIC

Communication and dissemination (CD) KPI_{ESCD}:

KPI_{ESCD}1: Number of organised Enlargement Workshops

KPI_{ESCD}2: Number of tailored partnership meetings with the participation of scientific community and/or decision-makers from target countries of the Enlargement Strategy

Enlargement of E-RIHS ERIC Members and Observers (MO) KPI_{ESMO}:

KPI_{ESMO}1: Number of Countries joining E-RIHS ERIC as Members

KPI_{ESMO}2: Number of Countries joining E-RIHS ERIC as Observers

Collaboration Agreements (CA) signed KPI_{ESCA}:

KPI_{ESCA}1: Number of MoU signed

KPI_{ESCA}2: Number of Partnership Agreements signed

8. CONCLUSIONS

The Enlargement Strategy defines the roles and actions within E-RIHS ERIC in order to provide efficient guidance for its global growth.

The key activities are focused on collaboration with the Enlargement Board that proved to be very efficient already within the implementation of the E-RIHS IP project. The Enlargement Board focuses on discussion and exchange of best practices on the establishment and functioning of a National Node; designing cooperation activities; discussion on common strategies; designing common communication and dissemination activities; discussion on measures and actions related to global challenges. These activities involve engagement of Director General, Central Hub, Committee of National Nodes and Heritage Science Academy.

The Director General as the legal representative of the E-RIS ERIC is empowered to lead negotiations with countries or individual institutions, sign Agreements and/or Memoranda of Understanding, facilitate meetings with relevant decision makers and scientific communities, issue endorsement letters, ensure the smooth integration of new Members or Observers, promote E-RIHS ERIC internationally and build diplomatic relationships. All these activities are assisted by the Central Hub, which also supports the Enlargement Board and monitors the key performance indicators for implementation of the E-RIHS ERIC Enlargement Strategy.

The Committee of National Nodes ensures that the scientific strategies and priorities of E-RIHS ERIC are harmonised with the strategies and priorities of new potential Members or Observers, resulting in a mutual added-value, collaborates with Director General in related tasks, well-established Nodes share their best practices with under preparation National Nodes by a twinning approach, guides the alignment with ESFRI principles, and helps in tailored events organisation.

The Heritage Science Academy promotes inclusion and international collaboration, as well as promotes E-RIHS best practices and access. Its training activities take place online or in hybrid format; in-person training programmes are organised in the form of workshops, doctoral schools and other types of hands-on training, which can be organised in also for the enlargement purposes. E-RIHS further promotes exchange of best talent by offering E-RIHS ERIC access to early career researchers in the domain of heritage science, and delivery of training initiatives through EU and international mobility programmes such as ERASMUS is also one of the goals of E-RIHS.

To secure the efficient global growth E-RIHS ERIC also prioritises its negotiations with new potential member countries in terms of their preparedness to join. A different approach is planned in relation to Member States, Associated Countries or Third Countries and individual organisations.

In order to enlarge the potential of E-RIHS ERIC to reach out and extend its possibilities for global growth, tailored communication and dissemination activities are planned that include organisation of Enlargement Workshops and tailored partnership meetings.

Monitoring the Enlargement Strategy goals will empower Director General to efficiently plan further activities.

The E-RIHS Enlargement Strategy drives E-RIHS's ambition to become a global research infrastructure, by facilitating engagement with new countries and organisations both within and beyond the European Union, thereby broadening the impact of E-RIHS and heritage science worldwide.

REFERENCES

- [1] D6.4 Report on Cooperation Activities, E-RIHS IP, 2024
- [2] D.11.1 E-RIHS Business Plan, E-RIHS PP, 2020
- [3] D6.2 Dissemination, Exploitation, and Communication strategy of E-RIHS ERIC, E-RIHS IP, 2024
- [4] <https://www.xofficio.eu/post/participation-of-non-eu-countries-in-an-eric-challenges-and-opportunities> (visited 08.07.2024)

ANNEX 1: FIRST ENLARGEMENT WORKSHOP

The first Enlargement Workshop: *"E-RIHS Enlargement Workshop: Extending Collaborations Inside and Outside Europe"* was organised in the frame of Task 2.2 in collaboration with Task 4.2. The Workshop was delivered online from the 17th of May until the 27th of May. The workshop was an opportunity to present E-RIHS to all international partners interested in joining or working with the infrastructure in the future. It presented E-RIHS and the long history of projects that prepared the infrastructure launch, its activities, its scientific vision, the development and improvement of the services offered, cutting-edge training opportunities, and different collaboration opportunities.

The workshop was divided into an opening introductory session on May 17th, 2024, geographical working sessions planned together with interested partners and a public closing session on May 27th, 2024.

The opening session was composed of several presentations of E-RIHS:

- Introduction (Piotr Targowski, Polish National Node of E-RIHS)
- Insight into E-RIHS: Mission, vision and activities (Vania Virgili, interim Director General of E-RIHS ERIC-to-be, Polonca Ropret, Chair of the Interim National Node of E-RIHS ERIC-to-be)
- 20 years of access: history and highlights (Brenda Doherty, Italian National Node of E-RIHS)
- Development and improvement of E-RIHS services, (Piotr Targowski, Polish National Node of E-RIHS)
- HS Academy, (Matija Strlič, Slovenian National Node of E-RIHS)
- E-RIHS collaboration opportunities and requirements (Rémi Petitcol, French National Node of E-RIHS, Paula Maria Carmona Quiroga, Spanish National Node of E-RIHS)

The separate bilateral working sessions were organised with Norway, Denmark, Austria, Brazil, Egypt, the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia, and United Arab Emirates in the week between 20th and 24th of May 2024. At the public closing session, the outcomes of bilateral working sessions were presented.

OUTCOMES OF THE WORKSHOP

Member States

Working session with Norway and Denmark:

Current status of E-RIHS in both countries was presented.

Further topics that were discussed:

- integration of a new national node within E-RIHS ERIC, as a unique access point
- joint policy development on Heritage Science (e.g. ethical materials sampling procedures, joint development of standardised protocols, data storage and copy right property)
- benefits that E-RIHS provides to academic and scientific institutions in terms of interdisciplinary research opportunities and advancements of science in general
- challenges of sustainability and environmental impact in the face of climate change

Working session with Austria:

The bilateral session was oriented in offering the advice on how to prepare the Consortium Agreement between Austrian partners to formalise an E-RIHS National Node.

Third Countries

Working session with Brazil:

Discussed topics:

- The situation of the Res Infra Plus project and the possibilities of participation of Antecipa as a community targeted group.
- The preparation of the G20 Culture in Brazil and the opportunities to promote collaboration between Antecipa and E-RIHS at a political level.
- Antecipa 's request for help to deal with the emergencies caused by the floods in Brazil
- Digital interoperability and databases for heritage sciences and the role of E-RIHS' Digilab platform.
- The training activities, conferences and workshops planned by Antecipa and the possibility of involving E-RIHS colleagues.
- The Into Past BR project approved by the Ministry of Science and Technology of Brazil and the potential for bilateral collaboration with European institutions.

General outcome: work towards MoU

Working session with Egypt:

Egyptian E-RIHS Network was presented and the discussion was oriented in the expectations of EGYPT from E-RIHS ERIC and the offers of EGYPT to the E-RIHS ERIC (presented in Annex 3).

General outcome: work towards MoU

Working session with the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia:

The Heritage Science activities of KSA were briefly presented and a short presentation of E-RIHS was given. It was agreed the E-RIHS needs to submit an official letter to the Heritage Commission CEO - Ministry of Culture, KSA to initiate collaboration with E-RIHS

Working session with United Arab Emirates:

Representatives from UAE – Abu Dhabi Emirate were present (representative of the Heritage & Art Sector at the Ministry of Culture) as well as colleagues from the scientific community (Louvre Abu Dhabi, different Universities)

- They are very much interested in collaboration with E-RIHS
- Possible topics for collaboration (pilot projects (e.g. modern heritage), training, etc.
- Will follow the Egyptian example
- Interested to sign a MoU with E-RIHS
- Further planning of next bilateral meetings.

ANNEX 2: TEMPLATE FOR MOU WITH THIRD COUNTRIES

MEMORANDUM OF UNDERSTANDING

BETWEEN

European Research Infrastructure for Heritage Science (E-RIHS)

AND

_____NAME OF INSTITUTION/GOVERNMENT_____

Each should be referred as “Signatory” or together as “Signatories”

Preamble

Within the framework of the establishment of the European Research Infrastructure for Heritage Science (E-RIHS) as a European Research Infrastructure Consortium (ERIC) regulated by Regulation (EC) No 723/2009, which is intended to foster excellence in heritage science, also through the strengthening of international cooperation with countries outside the European Union, and within bilateral meetings in the framework of E-RIHS Implementation Phase (HORIZON-INFRA-2021-DEV-02, Grant Agreement no. 101079148), interest have been expressed in identifying steps and actions towards formalizing a partnership within the E-RIHS ERIC.

The **European Research Infrastructure for Heritage Science (hereinafter referred to as E-RIHS)** is a pan-European distributed research infrastructure dedicated to furthering research and innovation in the interdisciplinary domain of heritage science, to better knowledge, conservation and appreciation of cultural heritage. E-RIHS is structured around National Nodes – coordinated by a Central Hub located in Florence, Italy – featuring fixed and mobile instruments at the national level of recognized excellence, physically accessible collections, archives and virtually accessible heritage data. With this organizational structure, E-RIHS strives to provide a broad array of state-of-the-art scientific equipment, advanced methodologies, data, training, repositories for standardized data storage, analysis and interpretation. The goal is to empower the community to progress in heritage science and enhance global access to its distributed facilities in a coordinated and efficient manner. The vision of E-RIHS is to ensure that heritage remains meaningful, relevant, and accessible in a diverse and changing world for the benefit of present and future citizens. Its mission is to serve the heritage science community by providing users, including both scholars and practitioners, with centrally managed access to expertise know-how, research capacity, and resources through four integrated physical and virtual platforms, namely ARCHLAB, on-site physical or digital archives of scientific information and reference collections; FIXLAB, fixed-located analytical facilities to study cultural heritage samples or movable objects; MOLAB, mobile labs and experts staff performing non-invasive and multi-diagnostic measurements of cultural heritage on-site; DIGILAB, virtual access to digital data repositories complemented with tools for creating new knowledge. ARCHLAB, MOLAB and FIXLAB have been already operational in previous European projects, while DIGILAB is currently in development.

The name of institution (country) works on

Article 1 – Purpose

The purpose of this Memorandum of Understanding (MoU) is to establish a framework for _____[institution (country)] to partner and/or to facilitate partnership with E-RIHS ERIC, towards strengthening international cooperation for the advancement of heritage science.

The Signatories shall jointly promote dialogue and discussion towards identifying the next steps within scientific cooperation and institutional arrangement towards achieving the above objective.

This MoU reflects the Signatories' intention to cooperate, expressed in good faith. This MoU is not intended to create rights or obligations under international or domestic law. This MoU is not a legally binding arrangement and does not represent nor does it intend to create any right or binding legal obligation or relation between the Signatories. Hence, without limitation, this MoU does not result in the establishment of any claims, financial implication, commitment, obligation or liability between the Signatories.

Article 2 – Activities

This MoU shall promote joint initiatives aimed at strengthening cooperation between _____[institution (country)] and E-RIHS (e.g., joint activities, sharing of expertise and best practices, and exchange programmes) with the ultimate goal to co-develop a partnership agreement towards enabling _____[institution (country)] (or its designated institution in _____Country) to join E-RIHS ERIC. The initiatives are described in the Annex Workplan, which is to be considered an integral part of this MoU.

Article 3 – Funding and resources

Subject to the availability of appropriate funds, each Signatory's representative shall normally bear the costs of its own participation in the cooperative activities. Furthermore, each Signatory covers its own administration costs regarding its contribution to the cooperative activities.

Persons involved in the cooperative activities under this MoU will have insurance cover at their own expenses or chargeable to their own Institution.

All the initiatives described under the present MoU shall be carried out in full compliance with the laws and regulations of each country and in observance of the international obligations.

Article 4 – Scientific Joint Committee

With a view to steer and oversee the implementation of MoU, a Scientific Joint Committee (SJC) will be established comprising representatives of the Signatories. The SJC will be co-chaired by the representative of both Signatories.

For E-RIHS, Name and role

For _____[institution (country)], ... Name and role

Ad hoc experts (e.g., Legal Advisor) can be called to advise the SJC, for particular issues related to further formalization of the cooperation between the Signatories.

Article 5 – Communication

The Signatories have identified the following focal points as entry point for communication:

NAME 1– EMAIL / ADDRESS co@e-rihs.eu

NAME 2 – EMAIL / ADDRESS

Article 6 – Confidentiality

Any information from this MoU shall be used only by the Signatories and for the objectives of this MoU and treated as strictly confidential by the Signatories. Any information on cooperation activities under this MoU shall not be disclosed to any third party without prior written agreement.

Article 7 – Jurisdiction

Any dispute resulting under this MoU shall be resolved amicably. Therefore, any dispute concerning the interpretation or execution of this MoU will be resolved through friendly consultation and negotiations between Signatories without the intervention of third Parties of international arbitration.

Article 8 – Amendments

Signatories may propose amendments to this MoU and its Annex Workplan. The amendments will require mutual written agreement by both Signatories, through exchange of official letters.

Article 9 – Duration and Termination

Upon signature by both Signatories, this MoU shall come into force.

Unless otherwise agreed, this MoU shall remain into force for a period of 3 (three) years, or until a formal partnership agreement within E-RIHS ERIC is reached.

Each Signatory can express its decision to terminate it through a certified notification.

Signed at _____(city)_____ in 2 (two) originals in the English language

Signed for and on behalf of E-RIHS

Signed for and on behalf ANTECIPA

Name

Name

Director General, E-RIHS

Title

Date

Date

ANNEX WORKPLAN

Within the framework of _____[institution (country)] Heritage Science activities, and its interest in joining E-RIHS ERIC as a prospective Strategic Partner, the following joint initiatives are planned to be carried out by the Signatories of the MoU.

ANNEX 3: COLLABORATION WITH BRAZIL AND EGYPT

3.1 Opportunities for collaboration with the Brazilian HS Infrastructure ANTECIPA

ANTECIPA (Associação Nacional de Pesquisa em Tecnologia e Ciência do Patrimônio/Brazilian National Association for Research in Technology and Heritage Science) was founded in December 2015 with the main objective of promoting the preservation of cultural heritage through interdisciplinary collaboration between individuals and institutions from several areas working in cultural heritage. ANTECIPA's integration with the European previous projects has been effective since EU-ARTECH, back in the years 2000, when LACICOR at the Federal University of Minas Gerais was invited to join.

The goals of ANTECIPA align with those of E-RIHS, aiming at the effective establishment of the Brazilian Research Infrastructure for Heritage Science, which will provide the necessary institutional national backbone for the implementation of the Consortium involving Universities, State Institutes for Cultural Heritage Protection, State Attorney's Office, Research Centres, Museums, Civil Society Organizations, and other stakeholders and interested parties.

The expectations of ANTECIPA from E-RIHS ERIC are:

- Access via bilateral or multilateral agreements to European infra-structure platforms
- Exchange of students, researchers and professionals via bilateral or multilateral agreements
- Exchange of experiences in tackling cultural heritage issues in diverse levels.
- Organization and promotion of joint events, workshops, congresses and schools.

ANTECIPA can offer to the E-RIHS ERIC:

- Access to all activities promoted by ANTECIPA
- Expertise of individuals and institutions
- Local cultural heritage issues and interesting problems
- Access to local infra-structure via bilateral or multilateral agreements
- Exchange of students, researchers, and professionals via bilateral or multilateral agreements
- Exchange of experiences in tackling cultural heritage issues in diverse levels.
- Organization and promotion of joint events, workshops, congresses and schools

3.2 Opportunities for collaboration with the Egyptian network of HS institutions

The Egyptian network of HS institutions is coordinated by Ain Shams University, Cairo with partners from Egyptian Atomic Energy Authority (EAEA), National Institute for Geophysics and Remote Sensing, Bibliotheca Alexandrina, Grand Egyptian Museum, National Museum of Egyptian Civilization, Fayoum University, Damietta University, Cairo University, and as a funding body Academy of Scientific Research and Technology – ASRT. The network of institutions is currently working towards the establishment of E-RIHS National Node.

The expectations of the Egyptian network from E-RIHS ERIC are:

- Access to research facilities
- Access to data and collections (Digital Lab)
- Advice on best practices
- Training and education
- Collaborative Research
- Consultation Services
- Technical Support
- Funding and Grants: EU and Erasmus
- Networking Opportunities
- Dissemination activities

Egypt can offer to the E-RIHS ERIC:

- Access to research infrastructure
- Access to rich heritage materials, sites, buildings, collections, archives etc.
- Gateway to broader Arab region and Africa
- Hosting summer/winter schools, trainings, workshops, conferences, and networking events.
- Public engagement with international visibility
- Collaborative research